

Q1 Do you conduct repeated MBES backscatter surveys?

Answered: 40 Skipped: 1

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
Yes	55.00% 22
No	45.00% 18
Total Respondents: 40	

Q2 Do you conduct repeated MBES backscatter surveys for the purpose of environmental monitoring?

Answered: 18 Skipped: 23

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Yes	72.22%	13
No	27.78%	5
Total Respondents: 18		

Q3 What kind of environmental monitoring?

Answered: 15 Skipped: 26

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
Habitat (biotic)	80.00% 12
Substrate type (abiotic)	86.67% 13
Anthropogenic impact (either biotic or abiotic)	53.33% 8
Total Respondents: 15	

#	OTHER (PLEASE SPECIFY)	DATE
1	Sometimes we do repeated backscatter surveys to get better resolution of the depth data (i.e. EM 712/710 surveys to replace EM 1002 data)	3/3/2020 10:15 AM
2	control of reference area	2/27/2020 5:06 PM

Q4 In which framework is this environmental monitoring conducted?

Answered: 16 Skipped: 25

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
Legal obligation	31.25% 5
Scientific research	68.75% 11
Technical research and development	43.75% 7
Hydrographic purposes	31.25% 5
Engineering project (e.g. construction works)	18.75% 3
Total Respondents: 16	

#	OTHER (PLEASE SPECIFY)	DATE
1	Marine Strategy Framework Directive MSFD	4/6/2020 2:19 PM

Q5 Over which temporal scales do you conduct repeated surveys?

Answered: 16 Skipped: 25

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
Short-term (hours, days, weeks)	25.00% 4
Medium-term (seasonal, months)	43.75% 7
Long-term (years, decades)	93.75% 15
Total Respondents: 16	

#	OTHER (PLEASE SPECIFY)	DATE
	There are no responses.	

Q6 Do you use a standard acquisition procedure? (eg BSWG guidelines/standard settings)

Answered: 17 Skipped: 24

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Yes	88.24%	15
No	11.76%	2
Total Respondents: 17		

Q7 Which software do you use for data acquisition?

Answered: 18 Skipped: 23

#	RESPONSES	DATE
1	QPS	4/9/2020 3:03 PM
2	mainly SIS & PDS, Command line in case of AUV driven by vendor-specific tools	4/7/2020 10:34 AM
3	SIS	4/6/2020 7:30 PM
4	SIS	4/6/2020 6:40 PM
5	Kongsberg SIS	4/6/2020 3:37 PM
6	SIS from Kongsberg	4/6/2020 2:19 PM
7	Hypack	4/6/2020 2:18 PM
8	SIS (Kongsberg)	3/10/2020 11:11 AM
9	Kongsberg GS	3/9/2020 9:07 AM
10	Kongsberg Seafloor Information Systems (SIS)	3/3/2020 10:15 AM
11	Kongsberg SIS	3/2/2020 9:56 AM
12	QINSy.	2/28/2020 9:17 AM
13	SIS and Qimera	2/28/2020 8:40 AM
14	Hypack	2/27/2020 7:05 PM
15	QINSy	2/27/2020 5:21 PM
16	SIS	2/27/2020 5:11 PM
17	SIS (KM)	2/27/2020 5:06 PM
18	SIS4	2/27/2020 4:33 PM

Q8 Do you use a standard processing procedure? (eg BSWG guidelines/standard settings)

Answered: 17 Skipped: 24

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Yes	76.47%	13
No	29.41%	5
Total Respondents: 17		

Q9 What software do you use to process MBES backscatter data?

Answered: 18 Skipped: 23

#	RESPONSES	DATE
1	QPS + MB-System + Custom	4/9/2020 3:03 PM
2	Fledermaus, CARIS, MB-System	4/7/2020 10:34 AM
3	FMGT	4/6/2020 7:30 PM
4	SonarScope	4/6/2020 6:40 PM
5	QPS QIMERA FMGT	4/6/2020 3:37 PM
6	CARSI HIPS and SIPS	4/6/2020 2:19 PM
7	FMGT	4/6/2020 2:18 PM
8	CARIS HIPS and SIPS	3/10/2020 11:11 AM
9	QPS Fledermaus Geocoder Toolbox	3/9/2020 9:07 AM
10	Fledermaus Geocoder Toolbox (have tested Caris Hips and Sips)	3/3/2020 10:15 AM
11	CARIS, Sonarscope	3/2/2020 9:56 AM
12	QINSy	2/28/2020 9:17 AM
13	FMGT	2/28/2020 8:40 AM
14	QPS FMGT	2/27/2020 7:05 PM
15	FMGT	2/27/2020 5:21 PM
16	QPS FMGT and SonarScope	2/27/2020 5:11 PM
17	SonarScope	2/27/2020 5:06 PM
18	FMGT	2/27/2020 4:33 PM

Q10 Is your processing software:

Answered: 18 Skipped: 23

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
Open Access	27.78% 5
Proprietary	94.44% 17
Other (please specify)	5.56% 1
Total Respondents: 18	

#	OTHER (PLEASE SPECIFY)	DATE
1	Does proprietary means commercial? If so, yes.	3/3/2020 10:15 AM

Q11 What kind of MBES backscatter calibration do you rely on?

Answered: 18 Skipped: 23

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Relative Calibration (e.g. control on a reference area or track)	55.56%	10
Absolute calibration (e.g. sphere calibration, tank calibration)	27.78%	5
No calibration	33.33%	6
Unsure	11.11%	2
Other (please specify)	16.67%	3
Total Respondents: 18		

#	OTHER (PLEASE SPECIFY)	DATE
1	Ground truth, if possible	4/7/2020 10:34 AM
2	Seabed sediment sampling	3/3/2020 10:15 AM
3	We use Teledyne-Reson T50P systems with the normalized snippet functionality	2/27/2020 7:05 PM

Q12 How do you merge backscatter data from different vessels, surveys and instruments (assuming the same frequency for all)—is there a specific strategy or approach that you utilize? Please specify:

Answered: 18 Skipped: 23

#	RESPONSES	DATE
1	I use the same vessel with same MBES system	4/9/2020 3:03 PM
2	We avoid to merge different instruments/sensors especially from different vendors.	4/7/2020 10:34 AM
3	often. Use relative normalization experiment to figure offsets between systems.	4/6/2020 7:30 PM
4	BS data acquisition on reference areas with various echosounders is applied for cross-calibration (calibrated SBES such as EK-80 vs MBES such as EM2040)	4/6/2020 6:40 PM
5	Approach Montereale Gavazzi 2019 ;)	4/6/2020 3:37 PM
6	There is not a specific strategy,	4/6/2020 2:19 PM
7	We don't since we don't use uncalibrated- we use backscatter and multispectral backscatter for relative changes within each survey to identify potential hard bottom and potential substrate type in comparison with ground truth data when necessary. But we use the same 3 multibeams so we do a sort of relative calibration process sometimes	4/6/2020 2:18 PM
8	We always use the same vessel for monitoring purposes	3/10/2020 11:11 AM
9	At the moment, I only have one system to collect data, so there is no need to merge different datasets.	3/9/2020 9:07 AM
10	It is a problem regarding backscatter. We do an adjustment in Fledermaus or ArcGIS, or nothing. Survey lines in reference areas show level changes in backscatter. By experience, it is difficult to have exactly the same sonar settings each time (not only the same ping mode, pulse form and dual swath mode, but other parameters as well). The guideline we use do not include settings for the other parameters, yet. Further, it is not only a change of instrument that influence the backscatter levels, but also a change of receiver within an instrument or a change of processing unit software (if this has included a change of frequencies).	3/3/2020 10:15 AM
11	We don't.	3/2/2020 9:56 AM
12	No specific approach	2/28/2020 9:17 AM
13	No real strategy, but strong interest to have one!	2/28/2020 8:40 AM
14	Have not had any immediate difficulties when merging Teledyne-Reson normalized snippets from different vessels/surveys/instruments.	2/27/2020 7:05 PM
15	No	2/27/2020 5:21 PM
16	Use of reference dB level at 45° of a reference area.	2/27/2020 5:11 PM
17	under study	2/27/2020 5:06 PM
18	Dont merge	2/27/2020 4:33 PM

Q13 Are you aware of the causes for backscatter variability?

Answered: 18 Skipped: 23

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
Yes	88.89% 16
No	5.56% 1
Unsure	5.56% 1
If "Unsure", please specify:	11.11% 2
Total Respondents: 18	

#	IF "UNSURE", PLEASE SPECIFY:	DATE
1	I'm unsure that I've seen much variability but as mentioned I don't tend to compare survey to survey	4/6/2020 2:18 PM
2	The above mentioned causes I know about, but not so much other causes (except for absorption and a physical change of the seabed surface).	3/3/2020 10:15 AM

Q14 Are you aware of the causes for backscatter variability between repeated surveys and within "snapshot in time" surveys?

Answered: 18 Skipped: 23

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Yes	77.78%	14
No	5.56%	1
Unsure	11.11%	2
If "Unsure", please specify:	22.22%	4
Total Respondents: 18		

#	IF "UNSURE", PLEASE SPECIFY:	DATE
1	Unsure with respect to effects in the very shallow survey areas, due to possibly varying attenuation over daytime and current cycles etc.	4/7/2020 10:34 AM
2	same as above- I just haven't done comparisons over long term we do relative within survey comparisons	4/6/2020 2:18 PM
3	I am not sure if you are referring to technical or environmental variabilities here	3/10/2020 11:11 AM
4	See answers to question 13 and 12.	3/3/2020 10:15 AM

Q15 What do you think are the causes of that variability?

Answered: 16 Skipped: 25

#	RESPONSES	DATE
1	assuming different surveys on the same area with same MBES system: Evironment condiction + incidence angle for mobile substrarte (assuming same survey lines for each survey)	4/9/2020 3:03 PM
2	In general? Different vendors and different approaches!! Environmental conditions. Alteration over the life-time of a transducer. Attenuation. Beam Pattern variations	4/7/2020 10:34 AM
3	stochastic, biological activity, uncorrected system offsets	4/6/2020 7:30 PM
4	The main one is due to the sediment substrate variability. The rest of the causes (sensor, acquisition) are quite well controled.	4/6/2020 6:40 PM
5	platform, instrument, and data acquisition/processing + environmental variability	4/6/2020 3:37 PM
6	Different instrument, different water conditions	4/6/2020 2:19 PM
7	I do not know if technical	3/10/2020 11:11 AM
8	Different calibration methods & acquisition set-ups	3/9/2020 9:07 AM
9	From the system itself (bias, attitude, lever arm, calibration, etc...), from the propagation in the medium (salinity variation, volumic reverberation, etc.), and from the seabed itself (patches, benthic life, etc.)	3/2/2020 9:56 AM
10	System, settings, environment (SVP/weather etc.), processing methods, visualisation software	2/28/2020 9:17 AM
11	turbidity, settings, tides, ...	2/28/2020 8:40 AM
12	Range of possibilities including environmental factors, sediment/substrate mobility and transport	2/27/2020 7:05 PM
13	1. Technical(setup, instrument), 2. Envionmental (real changes in habitat)	2/27/2020 5:21 PM
14	Environmental, instrumental and algorithmal	2/27/2020 5:11 PM
15	the system itself if isn't frequently calibrated or sediment changes or current effect (small ripples azimuth)	2/27/2020 5:06 PM
16	Variations in systems, changes in systems over time and variations in processing software	2/27/2020 4:33 PM

Q16 Do you consider the statistical variance intrinsic to the backscatter measurements?

Answered: 18 Skipped: 23

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
Yes	44.44% 8
No	27.78% 5
Unsure	27.78% 5
Other (please specify)	5.56% 1
Total Respondents: 18	

#	OTHER (PLEASE SPECIFY)	DATE
1	Angular response	2/27/2020 5:06 PM

Q17 Do you control the environmental variability during the survey?

Answered: 18 Skipped: 23

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Yes	61.11%	11
No	27.78%	5
Unsure	11.11%	2
If unsure, please specify why:	27.78%	5
Total Respondents: 18		

#	IF UNSURE, PLEASE SPECIFY WHY:	DATE
1	Not sure what is meant. Can one control the environmental variability? We record environmental conditions and when ever possible avoid invluence due to seasonal effects (if not part of the monitoring) or certain weather conditions (wind/rain). We don't for absorption/attenuation. We usually can not controll target geometry during scientific cruises, or at least just partly, due to other duties.	4/7/2020 10:34 AM
2	We should find a good way to efficiently keep track of environmental changes	4/6/2020 3:37 PM
3	as much as possible but realistically it's almost impossible...	4/6/2020 2:18 PM
4	We measure sound speed profiles quite often (every 30 minute approximately)	3/3/2020 10:15 AM
5	via SVP, no additional controls	2/28/2020 9:17 AM

Q18 Which environmental factors do you control/quantify?

Answered: 13 Skipped: 28

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Transmission losses: sound absorption in water (AlphaW)	84.62%	11
Transmission losses: sound absorption due to turbidity/suspended sediment (AlphaS)	23.08%	3
Target geometry: Survey azimuth orientation	76.92%	10
Other(s)	15.38%	2
Total Respondents: 13		

Q19 Which kind of MBES backscatter products/strategy do you use to detect/quantify changes of the seabed?

Answered: 16 Skipped: 25

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
Signal-based analysis	43.75% 7
Image-based analysis	56.25% 9
Ensemble approaches	12.50% 2
Time-series analysis	25.00% 4
Post-classification	43.75% 7
Pre-classification	12.50% 2
Spatial-change analysis (change detection)	12.50% 2
Other (please specify)	6.25% 1
Total Respondents: 16	

#	OTHER (PLEASE SPECIFY)	DATE
1	+/- all, see Montereale Gavazzi 2019 important to have good ground truthing (incl. boxcores in muddy Sands to muds) for validation	4/6/2020 3:37 PM

Q20 Do you carry out acoustic seafloor classification?

Answered: 18 Skipped: 23

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
Yes	77.78% 14
No	22.22% 4
Other (please specify)	5.56% 1
Total Respondents: 18	

#	OTHER (PLEASE SPECIFY)	DATE
1	relatively- not detailed	4/6/2020 2:18 PM

Q21 What do you use for classification/modelling?

Answered: 15 Skipped: 26

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Backscatter only	26.67%	4
Backscatter and derivatives	66.67%	10
If "Backscatter and derivatives", please specify which derivatives you use:	66.67%	10
Total Respondents: 15		

#	IF "BACKSCATTER AND DERIVATIVES", PLEASE SPECIFY WHICH DERIVATIVES YOU USE:	DATE
1	Angular response of multiple MBES pass over the same seafloor area	4/9/2020 3:03 PM
2	Multifrequency products if available and actually derivates not of backscatter but of bathymetry.	4/7/2020 10:34 AM
3	see Montereale Gavazzi 2019	4/6/2020 3:37 PM
4	Slope, Curvature, BPI	4/6/2020 2:19 PM
5	BS and DTM derivatives (rugosity, curvature, ...)	3/10/2020 11:11 AM
6	Angular Range Analysis (estimated grain size). The EM 710 data match quite well sediment samples of the seabed. EM 712 have far to high backscatter.	3/3/2020 10:15 AM
7	Seabed samplings	3/2/2020 9:56 AM
8	not necessarily derivatives from backscatter, but the MBES too. Also sidescan sonar, if available.	2/28/2020 9:17 AM
9	Bathymetric derivatives including slope, rugosity, curvature, etc.	2/27/2020 7:05 PM
10	Standard deviation, mean, texture parameters	2/27/2020 5:21 PM

Q22 How do you choose the variables to include in the multivariate classification?

Answered: 9 Skipped: 32

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Using a statistical feature selection procedure to identify only relevant variables	55.56%	5
Without a selection criteria	11.11%	1
Based on literature	66.67%	6
Based on personal judgment	55.56%	5
Other (please specify)	0.00%	0
Total Respondents: 9		

#	OTHER (PLEASE SPECIFY)	DATE
	There are no responses.	

Q23 Which software do you use to detect/quantify changes of the seabed?

Answered: 13 Skipped: 28

#	RESPONSES	DATE
1	custom	4/9/2020 3:06 PM
2	GIS, Fledermaus	4/7/2020 10:34 AM
3	FMGT	4/6/2020 7:30 PM
4	R or alternative	4/6/2020 3:57 PM
5	arcgis or manually	4/6/2020 2:21 PM
6	ArcGIS	4/6/2020 2:20 PM
7	ArcGIS, Cloudcompare, CARIS	3/10/2020 11:13 AM
8	QPS Qimera	3/9/2020 9:09 AM
9	Python, Sonarscope	3/2/2020 9:58 AM
10	ArcGIS	2/28/2020 9:20 AM
11	eCognition	2/27/2020 7:07 PM
12	Matlab	2/27/2020 5:23 PM
13	SonarScope	2/27/2020 5:07 PM

Q24 Ground truthing: Do you carry out ground-truthing in complement to the MBES backscatter?

Answered: 15 Skipped: 26

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Yes	100.00%	15
No	0.00%	0
Total Respondents: 15		

Q25 How do you plan the sampling?

Answered: 14 Skipped: 27

#	RESPONSES	DATE
1	stratified sampling technique over BS and Bathymetry variability (geomorphology)	4/9/2020 3:06 PM
2	Depends on the research, if possible stochastic, mostly related to other disciplines	4/7/2020 10:34 AM
3	from the backscatter mosaic	4/6/2020 7:30 PM
4	various	4/6/2020 3:57 PM
5	it is done by contract so not planned according to backscatter but backscatter is usually done as a compliment to samples (working on changing this)	4/6/2020 2:21 PM
6	according the backscatter signature	4/6/2020 2:20 PM
7	After seafloor classification	3/10/2020 11:13 AM
8	According to BS intensity and/or present morphology (MBES or SBP data)	3/9/2020 9:09 AM
9	Process backscatter in advance, check results from the Angular Range Analysis in Fledermaus, try to sample areas where the seabed, according to the range analysis, is not fine-grained (not silty or clayey - these areas are boring to sample...).	3/3/2020 10:16 AM
10	Several samplings in each BS-"homogeneous" areas	3/2/2020 9:58 AM
11	an agreed array (based on literature and regulators)	2/28/2020 9:20 AM
12	A priori, choosing random distribution of points. In practice, where is possible	2/27/2020 5:23 PM
13	according to the BS mosaic	2/27/2020 5:07 PM
14	ROV	2/27/2020 4:34 PM

Q26 Which ground-truthing equipment do you use?

Answered: 15 Skipped: 26

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Underwater videography	66.67%	10
Grab sampling	66.67%	10
A combination of equipment/methods	66.67%	10
Total Respondents: 15		

Q27 When analysing ground-truth data, which parameters do you measure or interpretation do you perform?

Answered: 15 Skipped: 26

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
Granulometric parameters	73.33% 11
Geotechnical parameters	13.33% 2
Qualitative parameters	73.33% 11
Terrain roughness	46.67% 7
Other (please specify)	26.67% 4
Total Respondents: 15	

#	OTHER (PLEASE SPECIFY)	DATE
1	spectral roughness from stereo images	4/9/2020 3:06 PM
2	species presence	3/10/2020 11:13 AM
3	Biogenic (benthic fauna) content	2/28/2020 9:20 AM
4	Visual coverage (especially for biological purpose)	2/27/2020 5:23 PM

Q28 Do you plan to conduct MBES backscatter repeated surveys?

Answered: 18 Skipped: 23

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Yes	55.56%	10
No	44.44%	8
Total Respondents: 18		

Q29 If so, for which purpose?

Answered: 10 Skipped: 31

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Monitoring habitat type	40.00%	4
Monitoring substrate type	50.00%	5
Monitoring anthropogenic impact	70.00%	7
Other (please specify)	10.00%	1
Total Respondents: 10		

#	OTHER (PLEASE SPECIFY)	DATE
1	Monitoring recovery from anthropogenic impact	3/4/2020 1:47 PM

Q30 In which framework is this environmental monitoring planned to be conducted?

Answered: 10 Skipped: 31

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
Legal obligation	30.00% 3
Scientific research	70.00% 7
Technical research and development	30.00% 3
Hydrographic purposes	30.00% 3
Engineering project (e.g. construction works)	10.00% 1
Other (please specify)	0.00% 0
Total Respondents: 10	

#	OTHER (PLEASE SPECIFY)	DATE
	There are no responses.	

Q31 Over which temporal scales are you planning to conduct the monitoring?

Answered: 10 Skipped: 31

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Short-term (hours, days, weeks)	10.00%	1
Medium-term (Months, seasonal)	50.00%	5
Long-term (year, decades)	40.00%	4
Total Respondents: 10		

Q32 If you don't conduct or don't plan to conduct MBES backscatter repeated surveys, please specify the reasons:

Answered: 6 Skipped: 35

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
Lack of expertise/methodologies	0.00% 0
Lack of sufficient guidelines	0.00% 0
incompatibility with other survey requirements	33.33% 2
No obligation	66.67% 4
No added value	16.67% 1
Lack of standardisation in backscatter (dB) values	16.67% 1
If "incompatibility with other survey requirements", please specify	33.33% 2
Total Respondents: 6	

#	IF "INCOMPATIBILITY WITH OTHER SURVEY REQUIREMENTS", PLEASE SPECIFY	DATE
1	We do not typically acquire MBES over the same area more than once.	4/7/2020 12:21 AM
2	Typically our work is trying to fill knowledge gaps in coverage and whilst it has been of interest for some time we typically are not doing times series. This is besides a harbor survey with repeats that we did for a student prac (see Schimel et al 2015) and some other opportunistic works where the focus has not been backscatter (we are still logging and processing it though).	4/6/2020 2:00 PM

Q33 Are you willing to take an active part in setting up a series of actions (see below) towards the Variability and Monitoring Backscatter Working Subgroup? (Even if you do not conduct, nor plan to conduct repeated MBES backscatter surveys?)

Answered: 31 Skipped: 10

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Yes	74.19%	23
No	25.81%	8
TOTAL		31

Q34 If yes, would you be willing to contribute to the following?

Answered: 24 Skipped: 17

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Share times series data and methodology (i.e. case studies)	62.50%	15
Setup a variability and monitoring experiment and report back to the group	54.17%	13
Process a common data set and report back to the group	70.83%	17
Total Respondents: 24		